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The impacts of collaborations in the development of Solid Oxide Fuel Cell technologies from 2000 to 2019: A bibliometric analysis

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Abstract

Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) technologies are receiving considerable interest due to their promising properties of achieving high-efficient and clean energy generation from a variety of fuels. Notwithstanding, the collaborative roles among researchers, institutions and countries in the development of SOFC technologies cannot be ignored. Accordingly, a bibliometric analysis was employed in this work to evaluate the global trends in SOFC research in terms of the numbers of output (number of publications) through scientific collaboration among authors and countries. A total of 14,330 publications including research articles and paper proceedings from 2000 to 2019 were obtained in the Web of Science database, with 90 countries actively contributing to SOFC research. Among these countries, China (3,164) had the strongest participation in terms of number of publications followed by the U.S.A. (2,566), Japan (1,387), South Korea (1,099) and Germany (777). The Asian continent had the highest percentage (45.77%) followed by Europe (30.85%) and North America (19.21%), while Africa had the least participation (0.59%). Additionally, the strongest partnership was seen between USA-China followed by China-Australia, USA-S.Korea, China-Sweden, and China-Japan. This study presents the likely factors influencing the active involvement of some countries and why others have low productivity in published SOFC research.

1. Introduction

The rapid population growth and the expansion of the world economy are greatly influencing global energy demand. Meanwhile the balance in the amount of energy demand is mainly covered by fossil fuel resources. For instance, the rise in energy demand in 2017 was reported to be 2.1%, whilst fossil fuels still accounted for about 81% of the total energy supply [1]. However, greenhouse gases such as CO₂ are emitted into the atmosphere during the combustion of fossil fuels, considerably impacting on climate. Moreover, the fluctuation in global oil prices and the uncertainty in the quantity of oil reserves are causing serious economic and energy security challenges to the world. Therefore, research into alternative and clean energy sources such as solar [2] and wind [3,4] has been intensified in recent times. Meanwhile, the need for an integrated system that uses a renewable energy source to produce hydrogen has been suggested since the energy generated from most of the alternative energy sources cannot be easily stored. The excess energy generated from these alternative sources is stored in form of hydrogen. Hydrogen is considered a feasible means of replacing fossil fuels and achieving a carbon-neutral economy [5,6]. The improved integration of renewable energy will also help in the smooth transitioning from fossil fuels into renewable energy or clean energy society.

In this regard, technologies that can utilise hydrogen for the production of clean and reliable power, such as fuel cells, are gaining increasing attention. Fuel cells have the advantages of improved efficiency, no moving parts, and potentially zero emissions at the point of use [7,8]. In particular, solid oxide fuel cell technology (SOFC) which was first initiated after Nernst discovered solid oxide electrolytes in 1899 [9], is considered an attractive technology for its high efficiency energy conversion [10], easy mode of operation since it does not require a liquid electrolyte [11] and its ability to operate with a wide range of fuels [12,13]. Solid oxide cells are operated at high temperature (700 to 900°C) which gives them the higher efficiency when employed compared to their counterparts when operated either as a fuel cell or as solid oxide electrolyser in reverse polarisation [14]. In addition to the high efficiency in electric energy generation, SOFCs generate high quality heat which can be utilised in other applications such as in heating for both domestic and industrial applications [15]. This unique feature of SOFC enables a broader modulation of heat/electricity ratio regardless of size [14]. Finally, the fuel flexibility and high efficiency of SOFC makes them attractive to countries with high dependency on fuel imports, since fuel use can be reduced and a range of renewable fuels exploited [16].

Nevertheless, SOFC technologies have not yet reached their full potential since they are preferably employed in stationary applications with very long required lifetimes (10 years, 40,000 hours of operation) [17]. Other factors include high manufacturing costs resulting in a still high product selling price. Although intensive research is ongoing to resolve the technical and economical issues associated with SOFC, factors such as funding, regulatory framework, market introduction subsidies, and government policies must also be considered and addressed in order to achieve full-scale commercialisation and global acceptability of these technologies. Collaboration among research groups in different countries is key to a technological success at a global level.

Therefore, this paper aims to study the influence of collaborative activity in the development of SOFC. Specifically, a bibliometric analysis was conducted by considering the research activities of countries and institutions around the world within a period of 20 years (2000 to 2019). In this study, the number of research publications and citations were employed as criteria for productivity in the area of SOFC technologies.

2. Methodology

Data for SOFC research was retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection Database on the 16th of July 2020. The WoS database was used for data collection since it is believed to hold relatively large volumes of data when compared to other sources [18,19]. The search for SOFC research outputs was restricted to research articles and proceeding papers to ensure that only research activity within the specified timeline was captured. The following search command was used in WoS to retrieve the required data:

Title: ("solid oxide fuel cell*" OR SOFC* or (solid AND Oxide AND Fuel AND Cell*)) AND Year published: (2000-2019) AND Document types: (Article OR Proceedings Paper) Timespan: 2000-2019. Indexes: SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, ESCI, CCR-EXPANDED, IC.

The asterisk on some of the searched words was to ensure all possible forms of the keywords were included. For example, SOFC* can be SOFC or SOFCs while cell* can be cell or cells. The quotation mark is to search for exact phrases in the keywords. After retrieving the data from WoS, it was imported to MS Excel where the total number of publications and citations were obtained. Furthermore, the data from WoS was also imported into the VOSViewer software where network visualisation of the co-authorship of individuals, countries, and institutions were created. In addition, the VOSViewer software was used to obtain the collaboration strengths of the participating countries and institutions. It should be noted that "title" was used rather than "topic" for the keywords search because "title" will give an approximate value of the total publications while topic may give an over-estimated value or what is known as false positive results [20,21]. This is because a keyword search using "topic" will include papers where the keywords appeared in abstracts and authors' keywords which may not be related to SOFC.

3. Results

In this section, findings from the bibliometric analysis conducted on SOFC research in the 2000 to 2019 period are presented.

3.1. Publication volume

The search for SOFC research based on articles and proceeding papers in WoS gave 14,330 total publications (TP) and 281,417 total citations (TC) as shown in Figure 1. As seen, there was a general rise in the number of citations per year, which indicates an increasing interest in SOFC research. This trend was likely triggered by the rising commercial interest in and expectations towards the technology. Moreover, the projected increase in the global market size of SOFC to reach USD 2.00 billion by 2026 may have been a driving force propelling research into this technology [22]. Similarly, there has been a relative increase in the number of publications since the year 2000 with a slight drop after 2011. This is probably due to a move of development into industry and therefore fewer publications.

Figure 1: Total number of publications and citations per year for SOFC research during 2000-2019.

3.2 Participating countries

90 countries were obtained from the retrieved documents. Among these countries, China had the highest number of publications (3,164) followed by the U.S.A. (2,566), Japan (1387), S.Korea (1099), and Germany (777). The size of the circles in the co-authorship network visualisation shown in Figure 2 indicates publication volume, and the thickness of the lines connecting the countries indicates the collaboration strengths among them [21]. In addition, the analysis of results using VOSViewer revealed that China had the strongest collaboration record (total link strength = 931) followed by the U.S.A. (741), and Germany (305). Considering the strength of the link between two countries (Table 1), the strongest collaboration was between China and the U.S.A., followed by China and Australia, U.S.A. and S.Korea, China and Sweden, and China and Japan. In terms of total citations, the U.S.A. was the most cited country (59,006), followed by China (53,007), Japan (20,069) and Germany (16,414).

Table 1: List of top 20 countries and top 20 co-authored countries in the order of decreasing collaboration strengths.

S/N	country	Total link strength per country	Collaboration between countries	Link strength between countries
1	China	931	China-U.S.A.	276.42
2	U.S.A.	741	China-Australia	157.83
3	Germany	305	U.S.A.-S.Korea	99.58
4	France	303	China-Sweden	75.37
5	Italy	290	China-Japan	67.67
6	S.Korea	257	U.S.A.-Japan	50.58
7	England	255	U.S.A.-Italy	48.00
8	Japan	246	China-Canada	47.83
9	Australia	234	China-France	47.33
10	Spain	203	China-Singapore	41.67
11	Canada	187	France-Spain	40.75
12	Sweden	168	France-Germany	36.62
13	Switzerland	150	Italy-England	33.33
14	Scotland	117	England-Spain	32.08
15	Denmark	108	Germany-Austria	30.20
16	Poland	94	China-England	29.58
17	Singapore	80	Germany-Switzerland	28.32
18	India	78	France-Italy	26.12
19	Brazil	75	Italy-Switzerland	25.33
20	Netherlands	75	U.S.A.-Germany	24.25

Figure 2: Co-authorship network visualisation of countries with a minimum of 20 publications on SOFC research within the time span 2000 to 2019.

Figure 3: The activities of continents in SOFC research within 2000 to 2019.

One of the factors that influences the development of SOFC technologies in any country will be government policies, which help in changing the public perception and acceptability, but also the economic viability of technologies. For instance, Japan is among the top ranked countries that are actively involved in SOFC development. Due to the scarcity of indigenous energy resources, Japan has been conducting an intensive funding programme in alternative and efficient energy solutions over the past two decades, in which SOFC gained focus in the country. Today, Japan is strongly established in SOFC technologies. SOFC technologies became popular owing to the flexibility of fuels,

specifically being able to use natural gas with no or minimal processing. The least participating countries, especially the developing countries, must take decisive steps and efforts to invest heavily in hydrogen, green fuel, and fuel cell technologies as an alternative to the conventional fossil fuels based energy system in order to join the efforts for tackling climate change.

High productivity is seen in continents such as Asia, Europe, and North America in SOFC development (Figure 3) and is mainly due to factors such as government policies which include strict regulations on emission of greenhouse gases, market introduction incentives, and funding in research relating to green energy [23,24]. For instance, the U.S.A. recently announced a new funding through the US Department of Energy's Office of Fossil Energy of up to \$30 million for the improvement of small-scale SOFC systems and hybrid energy systems [25]. This fund will further strengthen the participation of the U.S.A., which is already among the leading countries in SOFC research. Similarly, China, Japan, and other leading countries have a set of incentives in the form of subsidies to local manufacturers and key players in the energy sector, which has helped in consolidating their progress in advanced energy research and associated technologies over the years. Lastly, there is a strong collaboration among the leading countries as seen in the visualisation network represented in Figure 2 and Table 1. Meanwhile, the aforementioned factors, especially research collaboration, are lacking in African countries, which is why the region has low productivity in this aspect.

Notwithstanding, it will be economically important to look into the low participating continents, especially Africa, considering the enormous natural gas present in the region. The competition among the leading continents may get stiffer due to the projected boom in the market size of SOFC. The penetration of SOFC technology into Africa will require strong collaboration among the large international and local companies, an increased funding into SOFC research, government policies and incentives, and increased awareness in order to boost the acceptability of the technology. A successful penetration will greatly influence the global market size since Africa has the advantage of large population, which means potentially high selling volume of SOFC units in the region.

3.3 Participation of institutions

The initial result obtained from WoS indicated that 3,674 institutions participated in SOFC research. This value dropped to 3,624 after vetting the results due to some repeated institutions whose names appeared in different variations. The Chinese Academy of Science had the highest productivity in terms of number of publications followed by the University of Science & Technology China, Harbin Institute of Technology, and Forschungszentrum Juelich (Table 2). Overall, the highly active institutions were found in Asia, Europe, USA, and Australia while none of the institutions in Africa made it to the top 20. Moreover, the collaboration strengths of the various institutions followed a similar pattern as shown in Table 3. This trend further iterates the importance of collaboration in the development of SOFC. In order to demonstrate the general importance of cooperation, the following partnerships that were announced in 2016 shall be listed here, although they mostly do not refer to SOFC technology [26]:

- PowerCell Sweden AB and Swiss Hydrogen SA collaborated to manufacture and sell fuel cell systems according to the PowerCell's stacks for mobile and stationary applications.
- Ballard Power Systems and Toyota Tsusho Corporation partnered to enable Toyota Tsusho Corporation be a distributor of Ballard fuel cell products in Japan through 2020.

- US Hybrid and Sumitomo Corporation entered into a partnership for the increase in production capacity of fuel cell stacks for fuel cell engines and integrated vehicle technologies.
- IMS ECUBES and Arcola Energy announced a Joint Venture to develop hydrogen and fuel cell energy and mobility solutions for Europe and South Asia.
- Honda R&D Co. Ltd. and Ceres Power started collaborating to develop SOFC stacks using Ceres Power's Steel Cell technology.

The collaborative plan between Ceres Power, a UK-based company in the frontline of SOFC technology, and Weichai Power, a leading automobile and equipment manufacturing company in China, first announced in May 2018, has been concluded. The agreement included the commitment to establish a fuel cell manufacturing joint venture (JV) in Shandong Province, China [27]. Ceres Power also entered into a licensing agreement estimated as £8 million with Doosan Corporation, a Korea-based company in July 2019 to jointly develop SOFC power systems that are expected to balance the excess demands of S.Korea's commercial building market [22]. In the same month of July 2019, two companies in Japan, Mitsubishi Hitachi Power Systems and NGK Spark Plug entered into a partnership for the manufacturing and sale of cylindrical cell SOFC stacks which are the main components in power generation systems [22]. It is noteworthy that the aforementioned partnerships are only a few of the numerous ones entered among large companies, which are mainly based in the continents that are highly active in SOFC research.

On the other hand, only few countries in Africa have been able to enter into partnerships with some of the leading companies in SOFC technologies. For example, U.S.A.-based Dominovas Energy entered into a partnership with Delphi Automotive Systems to provide a 3 MW electricity plant to the City of David (a public-private partnership) in the Democratic Republic of Congo by employing its modular, off-grid Rubicon™ solid oxide fuel cell system [28]. In 2016, Dominovas Energy and a South Africa-based Edison Power Group, in partnership with Austria-based AVL GmbH (for system integration) and Italy-based SOLIDpower (for stack supply), launched a 50 kW unit RUBICON™ system in South Africa [29]. Dominovas Energy and Edison Power Group also entered into a partnership to develop a fuel cell system with a minimum of 50 MW capacity operating in sub-Saharan Africa over a period of 5 years, based on Dominovas Energy's RUBICON™ fuel cell system [29].

For a rapid development to take place in the area of SOFC technologies globally, considerable financial incentives, and strong partnership is required. In particular, African countries must implement policies that encourage technologies that enable the scale up of renewable energy supply, the introduction of more efficient energy conversion, and discourage energy from fossil fuels. In addition, more collaboration and technology transfer should be encouraged among the leading institutions or companies and the low participating countries to ensure speedy progress in SOFC research worldwide. It is worth mentioning that some challenges are encountered when conducting a bibliometric analysis. First, institution names can appear in both full and abbreviated forms which will cause WoS to treat them as separate institutions, which can lead to false positive results [20]. Secondly, not all journals are indexed in WoS. Consequently, those journals not indexed in WoS will be unintentionally omitted in a bibliometric analysis where WoS database was employed. The authors identified these challenges and ensured that they are minimised to an acceptable level.

Table 2: Publication status of the top 20 institutions that are actively participating in SOFC research according to number of publication within the timeline 2000 to 2019.

S/N	Names of Institutions	Country of Institution	Total Publications (TP)	Total Citations (TC)
1	Chinese Acad Sci	China	406	6908
2	Univ Sci & Technol China	China	349	8102
3	Harbin Inst Technol	China	277	4723
4	Forschungszentrum Julich	Germany	277	6744
5	Huazhong Univ Sci & Technol	China	268	4577
6	Natl Inst Adv Ind Sci & Technol	Japan	252	4527
7	Kyushu Univ	Japan	250	3390
8	Imperial College London	England	248	6946
9	Univ South Carolina	U.S.A.	215	4696
10	Tech Univ Denmark	Denmark	207	4966
11	Curtin Univ	Australia	194	3333
12	Georgia Inst Technol	U.S.A.	176	6245
13	Korea Inst Sci & Technol	S.Korea	162	2712
14	Pacific Nw Natl Lab	U.S.A.	159	4016
15	Jilin Univ	China	151	3957
16	Nanjing Univ Technol	China	146	4415
17	Nanyang Technol Univ	Singapore	145	5435
18	Tsinghua Univ	China	138	2434
19	Univ St Andrews	Scotland	136	3819
20	Univ Alberta	U.S.A.	130	2940

Figure 4: Co-authorship network of the top 20 institutions actively participating in SOFC research according to number of publication within the timeline 2000 to 2019.

Table 3: Top 20 institutions with strong collaboration strengths in SOFC research within the timeline 2000 to 2019.

S/N	Institutions	Country of Institution	Total link strength
1	Chinese Acad Sci	China	239
2	Univ Sci & Technol China	China	211
3	Harbin Inst Technol	China	163
4	Huazhong Univ Sci & Technol	China	161
5	Natl Inst Adv Ind Sci & Technol	Japan	152
6	Curtin Univ	Australia	133
7	Forschungszentrum Julich	Germany	130
8	Korea Inst Sci & Technol	South Korea	124
9	Georgia Inst Technol	U.S.A.	120
10	Jilin Univ	China	120
11	Kyushu Univ	Japan	113
12	Csic	Spain	103
13	Tsinghua Univ	China	98
14	Imperial College London	England	94
15	Nanyang Technol Univ	China	94
16	Univ St Andrews	Scotland	94
17	Tech Univ Denmark	Denmark	92
18	Univ S Carolina	U.S.A.	87
19	Chulalongkorn Univ	Thailand	87
20	Univ Alberta	U.S.A.	82

4. Conclusions

A bibliometric analysis was conducted to identify the impacts of collaborations in the development of solid oxide fuel cell technologies within the timeline 2000 to 2019. It was found that the most productive countries were from Asia, Europe and North America, while African countries had the least productivity in SOFC research. Findings further revealed that the leading countries have strong collaboration among themselves, which is most likely responsible for the very high productivity. The level of partnership between the top countries and institutions with those in Africa is very low which is due to unfavourable government policies and fear of uncertainties in investment. Therefore, the governments of the countries low in participating numbers must implement policies that enable investment in SOFC technologies and support international collaboration.

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